

Spin, Lorentz Invariant Equation for Free Probability and Lorentz Invariant Physical Equation

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Oct. 11, 2025

In this note, we suggest that a fundamental idea of free particle quantum mechanics is the wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ which we call a complex probability. This probability, however, does not describe the full physics of a free object. For example, it does not tell one if the object has rest mass or not, or whether it has electric and magnetic fields as in the case of a photon. Thus, we suggest that there must exist a Lorentz scalar equation describing the full physics of the problem, but that this equation makes use of the probability $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$, but not necessarily in a linear form (as in the continuity equation of energy density and Poynting momentum for a photon).

At the same time $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ is an eigenfunction of linear operators $i \frac{d}{dt}$ partial and $-i \text{grad}$ partial. Thus, we postulate that at the root of any physical Lorentz invariant equation using functions based on $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$, there should be a corresponding Lorentz scalar equation in $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$. Such an equation must be based on the operators $i \frac{d}{dt}$ partial and $-i \text{grad}$ partial, but as a Lorentz scalar, it must contain an operator which forms a dot product with $-i \text{grad}$. If p_x, p_y, p_z and E are the pieces of information of interest, then this new vector is not based on x -space etc, but may be a set of matrices which allow this invariant base equation to become the Lorentz scalar physical equation. In other words, one needs to add a kind of geometry to $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ to allow it to describe the full physics of a problem. This geometry seems to be hidden in the way the E, p_x, p_y and p_z variables are interrelated. We consider both the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ and spin 1 photon cases.

Quantum Free Particle and $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$

In previous notes, we argued that given a collision of E_1, E_2 and p_1, p_2 with conservation of both, one does not know the outcome values E_i, E_k and p_k, p_l (one dimension). If one assumes equal probability for any pair which maintains conservation, then one would expect a probability of the form:

$$\exp(i E) \text{ and } \exp(i p) \text{ one dimension } ((1))$$

"I" is used because the probability of a free particle cannot be real, i.e. one does have any weight as in an ideal gas. $\exp(ip)$ and $\exp(-ip)$, however, must have the same value and so ((1)) cannot be correct. One must combine p with a variable which also changes when one changes the direction of the x axis. This suggests then:

$$\exp(-iEt) \text{ and } \exp(ipx) \text{ to have an overall Lorentz invariant scalar probability } ((2))$$

A fundamental issue now arises. The probability $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ does not describe the full properties of a free object. For example, $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ could apply to a particle with rest mass or a photon with no rest mass.

A particle with rest mass is described by the Lorentz invariant scalar equation:

$$-E^2 = c^2 \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} + m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((3))$$

A photon is described by both: $E = c |\mathbf{p}|$ ((4))

as well as an equation using electric and magnetic fields, i.e.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} (\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{\mu_0} \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}) + \frac{1}{\mu_0} \text{grad} \cdot \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad ((5))$$

((5)) depends on $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ through $\mathbf{E} = C_1 \text{Real} (\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}) \text{ vector along } \mathbf{r})$

and $\mathbf{B} = C_2 \text{Real} (\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}) \text{ vector along } \mathbf{r})$ ((6))

((3)) is nonlinear in the operators $\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial}$ and $-i \text{grad} \text{partial}$, but linear acting on $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$, whereas ((5)) is linear in the operators $\frac{d}{dt}$ and $-i \text{grad}$, but quadratic in the probability $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$.

We postulate the following. We argue that the free object probability $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ is a key underlying partial description of a free object. It is an eigenfunction of $\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial}$ and $-i \text{grad} \text{partial}$, but is missing information contained in equations such as ((3)) and ((5)). We suggest that just as ((3)) and ((5)) are Lorentz invariant equations which make use of the E, p_x, p_y, p_z , there must exist a Lorentz scalar equation, linear in $\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial}$, $-i \text{grad} \text{partial}$ for $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$. Furthermore, this equation for the probability must be the foundation upon which one may create the more general physical equations such as ((3)) or ((5)). The two equations cannot be independent.

This suggests that one must find a vector to use in a dot product with \mathbf{p} (or $-i \text{grad}$). This vector, however, does not seem to be the \mathbf{r} vector or any other physical vector. Instead, it seems that it is required to describe a kind of hidden geometry in the problem. To see this specifically, we consider an abstract math vector consisting of matrices. In such a case, one should have:

$$-m_0 \text{Matrix } A + \text{Matrix } 0 (\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial}) + \sum_{i=1,2,3} \text{Matrix } -i (\frac{d}{dx}) \} \exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}) \text{ object} = 0 \quad ((7))$$

((7)) must be a building block equation for ((3)), with the obvious operation being the multiplication of both sides of ((7)). This yields various conditions for the matrices. Dirac has already solved this problem and found that the:

$\text{Matrix } -i (i=1,2,3)$ are 4x4 matrices with the Pauli 2x2 spin matrices on the anti-diagonal, with the second one appearing with a minus sign. ((8))

The point is that we suggest that ((7)) should exist a priori because there must be a Lorentz scalar equation in $\frac{d}{dt}$ and $-i \text{grad}$ acting on $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ and ((3)) cannot be independent of this equation.

If this is the case, then one should be able to use ((7)) with $m_0=0$ for a photon. The same basic building block idea should hold. In a previous note, we have shown that one may take ((5)) and linearize it by factoring out Electric field + i B field to obtain:

$$d/dt (E+iB) + e_{ijk} d/dx_k (E+iB) \quad ((9))$$

Here e_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol and ij are the matrix entries, while $k=1,2,3$ describes the matrix itself. As a result, the geometry is different in ((9)) because the physical Lorentz scalar equation ((5)) differs from ((3)).

In other words, spin describes in a geometrical manner how a basic building block equation linear in d/dt and $-i \text{ grad}$ acting on $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ with a vector or matrix M_i dotted with d/dx_i may be used to create the Lorentz scalar physical equation as the two cannot be independent.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to understand how spin arises. We suggest that without considering any quantum mechanical free particle features, there exist physical equations such as ((3)) and ((5)) for a particle with rest mass and a photon described in terms of electric and magnetic fields. These are Lorentz invariant equations.

We next suggest that the quantum mechanical feature of a free object follows from postulating that a given E_1, E_2, p_1, p_2 (one dimension) can create any E_i, E_j, p_l, p_k outcome pairs with equal probability as long as energy and momentum are conserved. We then argue that the probability must be described by $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ which is a Lorentz invariant. Thus, the physical Lorentz scalar equations ((3)) and ((5)) actually depend on $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$, but this does not mean that the operators d/dt and $-i \text{ grad}$ appear linearly (they do in ((5)) but not in ((3))). Nor does it mean that $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ appears linearly (it does in ((3)), but not in ((5))).

We suggest that $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ is an eigenfunction of $-i d/dt$ partial and $i \text{ grad}$ partial and so there should exist a Lorentz scalar equation for $\exp(-iEt- i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$. We further suggest that the vector $-i \text{ grad}$ should form a dot product with a math vector of matrices. This Lorentz scalar equation for $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ would then serve as the building block for the physical Lorentz scalar equation, as the two cannot be independent. Thus, the vector of matrices determines what physical Lorentz scalar equation results from a building block $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ with matrices equation. In the case of ((3)), the matrices linked with \mathbf{p} are 4×4 one with 2×2 Pauli matrices along the diagonal with the second matrix having a factor of -1 . In the case of ((5)), e_{ijk} is the matrix with i, j representing the matrix elements. In other words, the spin form describes a hidden geometry required to convert the building block Lorentz scalar equation for $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ into the physical Lorentz scalar equation.